

INTEGRATING NARRATIVES IN ENERGY MODELLING: SOCIAL ASPECTS OF THE ENERGY TRANSITION IN SPAIN

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ABSTRACT

The energy transition requires navigating complex social, political, and economic uncertainties which are examined through energy and environmental modelling exercises that explore alternative energy pathways. However, they do not systematically include social and political aspects. This study addresses the gap in the literature by exploring the integration of environmental perceptions alongside social and political aspects into modelling. By examining different qualitative storylines of governance logics of diverse actors of the Spanish energy transition (government, market, and civil society), this study translated them into quantitative parameters which will allow their integration into energy models and environmental impact assessments related to the energy transition. We used different data sources to inform the storylines such as a national survey planned to be conducted in March 2024 on diverse regions of Spain to gather a representative sample of the public perception of the energy transition policies, stakeholder engagement, in-depth interviews, and policies. The resulting datasets which are reflective of the social dimensions of the energy transition in Spain will have two objectives: integration into the Calliope-ENBIOS suit, modelling tools for the assessment of energy transition scenarios, and inclusion in the socio-political modelling toolbox QTDIAN. The expected results are to reveal how environmental perceptions, along with social and political factors, influence public acceptance, policy choices and potential environmental impacts of different energy transition pathways in Spain. This study will allow us to move beyond purely technical analysis and capture the holistic dynamics of the transition. The latter can inform more equitable and sustainable policymaking.

INTRODUCTION

To achieve the targets for the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions and reach climate neutrality, as envisioned in the European Green Deal and the Paris Agreement, societies must undergo a multi-dimensional fundamental transformation. At the core of the latter is the energy transition which requires a significant structural change in the energy systems aiming for renewable and sustainable sources. This process, however, entails high uncertainty regarding technical, political, economic, environmental, and societal dimensions (Moallemi et al., 2017). To navigate this uncertainty and inform decision-making, exploratory modelling analyses uncertainties using computational exercises (Moallemi et al., 2017). Based on these energy models, policymakers and stakeholders explore possible energy futures, i.e. scenarios to achieve the targets and comply with the implemented energy policies at international, national, and regional levels. Despite the fundamental transformation of the current energy systems in recent years, the models producing the scenarios address only a limited number of aspects focusing mainly on technological, economic and in some cases environmental aspects as they seek cost-optimal futures (Trutnevyte et al., 2014; Süsser et al., 2022). Hence, energy models do not systematically include social aspects as they are either ignored or considered exogenous to the models (Süßer et al., 2022; Trutnevyte et al., 2019). There is a growing recognition in the literature

that the models must include diverse aspects that could capture the complex dynamics of the energy transition, especially environmental and social aspects, and accordingly, new models are progressively incorporating these dimensions. Failure to consider social and environmental factors of the energy transition and not including them in the energy modelling may lead to irrelevant and unfeasible energy policies, biased policy recommendations and adverse environmental impacts(Süsser et al., 2022).

At a national level, Spain published its Integrated National Plan for Energy and Climate (INPEC 2021-2030) in 2020 presenting the country's commitments on climate and energy for the year 2030 while also complying with the objectives of the European Green Deal. Since then, numerous legislative proposals have been presented and approved at the European level, increasing the level of ambition in terms of climate change, and this has been reflected in the European Climate Law and the "Fit for 55" packages and "REPowerEU" packages. As a result, in 2023 Spain updated its energy and climate plan (INPEC 2023-2030) to meet the objectives of the European Union. This policy has been informed by the TIMES-Spain, which is a techno-economic energy optimisation model belonging to the TIMES models developed by the International Energy Agency (IEA). This analytical tool for energy policy assessment in Spain is by definition focused on technical and economic factors and it does not capture the social dynamics of energy transition in Spain. This might result in difficult social acceptance of the implementation of the energy policies at a national and regional level and a lack of social equity.

The environmental impacts of energy transition scenarios have also been examined, mostly from the field of Life Cycle Assessment (Laurent et al., 2017; Lucas et al. 2013). However, these studies fail to include social perceptions about environmental issues in two ways. First, and by definition, they are modelling approaches based on technical and environmental aspects only. Second, they result in a list of environmental indicators that are difficult to compare with one another. In this second case, the lack of valuation and ranking of those environmental impacts hinders policymaking and may result in policies that prioritise environmental values that are not in agreement with those of the general public.

We find two challenges: the lack of social storylines to help design the energy system and the lack of knowledge about environmental valuation that can assist decision-making. To address this gap, this study examines the research question: ***What indicators should be included in energy and environmental modelling to accurately reflect the social reality of the energy transition in Spain?*** It aims to fill this void by exploring narratives about energy transition and environmental impacts in Spain. This study is based on Foxon's (2013) conceptualisation that transition pathways arise through the dynamic interaction of technological and social factors at and between different levels, mediated by the actions of actors. These actors have different governance logics and framings of the key energy challenges and choices that shape the energy transition. Foxon (2013) defines three types of actors that influence change: government, market, and civil society actors. Taking as a foundation these three governance logics, this study identifies the narratives behind them by developing three storylines: government-led, market-centred, and people-powered storylines which explore the three different transition pathways describing possible low-carbon futures. The latter contributes to the discovery of themes capturing the social dynamics which are translated into quantifiable indicators that can be integrated into the energy modelling tools.

METHODS

This study recognises that the energy transition occurs through a dynamic interaction between different levels. Thus, it is based on the theoretical framework of the multi-level perspective of Geels (2011) which conceptualises socio-technical transitions as an interplay between three analytical levels: niche (the locus of radical innovations, learning processes and social networks), socio-technical regimes (the locus of established practices and associated rules that stabilise the existing system) and an exogenous socio-technical landscape. ***Transitional pathways or socio-technical storylines*** derive from the multi-level perspective. They examine the interaction between key actors associated with the coevolution of technologies, institutions, business practices and strategies across levels (Trutnevyte, 2019; Robertson, 2017; Foxon et al., 2010). Based on this understanding, Foxon et al. (2010) and Foxon (2013) examine the governance patterns of different actors and how they affect technological, institutional, and social change. The latter is important as the decisions and behaviours of key actors can influence the process of change and the outcome of the

energy transitions. Therefore, this study uses Foxon's (2013) understanding of governance which refers to structures and processes that influence decisions made by different actors within the system. The governance includes national and local policymakers, large firms, end-users and how their choices influence the system. These diverse actors have a different understanding of the key energy challenges (Foxon, 2013) Thus, this study examines three governance logics which represent the perspectives of the three main actors involved in the energy transition: government, market, and civil society. Based on their storylines representing the three governance logics, the uncertainty around the actors' preferences, values, and acceptance is uncovered.

There is a consensus in energy research that the social dimension will play a pivotal role in shaping energy transitions (Weimer-Jehle et al. 2020). In energy scenario construction, this is recognised through the approach of informing the energy models with storylines about the societal future (Weimer-Jehle et al. 2020). This paper uses the Moallemi et al. (2017) definition of *narrative*, a coherent storyline describing how the energy transition unfolds (through an initial state of the energy system, internal and external mechanisms of change and the new state of the energy system) and understands a *storyline* as a qualitative narrative of detailed descriptions of possible energy futures (Süsser et al. 2021). Hence, here, the concepts of narrative and storyline are interchangeable. They play an essential role when there is high uncertainty or when information cannot be entirely quantified (Fortes et al. 2015). Additionally, storylines serve to improve and complete model-based energy analyses and integrate stakeholders' views, which might result in higher social acceptance of the energy transition processes. They go beyond model insights and facilitate communication of the results of scenario exercises (Weimer-Jehle et al. 2020).

To achieve the study's objective of integrating the social aspects of the Spanish energy transition into modelling, this study uses the iterating strategy. It follows the two-step iterative approach. **The first step** consists of translating the qualitative storylines into a set of harmonised quantitative assumptions needed for conducting the model runs. As recommended by Trutnevyte (2014), this quantitative input should be a narrower representation of the storyline with a small number of assumptions while also allowing flexibility for quantitative models to express their perspectives. Specific aspects of the storyline shall be scrutinised so that key variables and themes are identified and later translated into quantitative input assumptions. In **the second step**, after the model runs, each qualitative statement of the governance logics specified in the storyline is compared and contrasted with the models (Trutnevyte, 2014). This step of revision of the storylines is needed as it detects inconsistencies and omitted aspects. There is a certain level of subjectivity involved in the process of translation, as one qualitative assumption could have a range of quantitative representations (Trutnevyte, 2014). Hence, to avoid this limitation, this study relies on an interdisciplinary team with environmental science, modelling and social science background that ensures the robustness and feasibility of the translation process.

The resulting datasets will have two objectives: First, the quantified parameters capturing the social and political aspects and the environmental perceptions of the energy transition in Spain will be integrated into the energy system optimisation tool Calliope (Pfenninger and Pickering, 2018) and ENBIOS (Madrid-López et al.), a simulation tool for the assessment of environmental impacts and resource requirements of energy system pathways. Second, these datasets will also be included in the socio-political modelling toolbox QTDIAN developed in the SENTINEL project (Mayer et al., 2024).

This study combines diverse methods to capture the complexity of interaction between the social factors, technologies, actors, and their respective governance logic to develop the storylines. Two participatory expert workshops were conducted in May 2022 and October 2023 with diverse stakeholders from the energy transition in Spain such as experts from the government, market, and civil society to grasp the general perspectives on the matter. Additional methods were employed to complement each storyline. For the government-led storyline, in-depth interviews were conducted with policymakers, and discourse analysis of energy policies, campaigns, and government initiatives. The market-centred storyline was analysed through a case study of one of the biggest energy companies in Spain, Iberdrola. Their company's reports and in-depth interviews with the company's experts contributed to the storyline development. For the civil society storyline, complementing the analysis of advocacy materials will be a national survey that will be conducted in March 2024. It aims to gather quantitative data on public perceptions of the energy transition in Spain, focusing specifically on environmental concerns. The target audience will be representative of the Spanish population,

encompassing diverse ages, gender, and location. The survey will collect data regarding diverse issues among which the perceived severity of environmental problems, and concerns about potential environmental impacts (land use change, water usage, visual impact of renewable energy projects).

EXPECTED RESULTS

Three distinct storylines were employed, each aligned with a specific governance logic. Analysing government policy documents, market reports, civil society advocacy materials, output from the participatory workshops and a national survey which will be conducted in March, we have found the following provisional results.

The technocratic efficiency (government-led) storyline aligns with the Integrated National Plan on Energy and Climate (INPEC 2021-2030) and the newly published draft of its updated version INPEC 2023-2030, which is a response to the increase in climate ambition at the European level. Spain’s climate and energy targets focus on a 32% reduction in greenhouse gas emissions compared to 1990, 48% of renewables on the final use of energy, 44% improvement in energy efficiency in terms of final energy, 81% renewable energy in electricity generation and a reduction of energy dependency up to 51% by 2030 (MITECO, 2023). Thus, the government-led storyline prioritises centralised planning and cost-effectiveness to accomplish the climate objectives at the national and European levels. The policies focus on standardised renewable energy projects, stringent carbon pricing and accelerated grid modernization. **The market-driven transformation (market-centred) storyline** echoes the reports from companies like Iberdrola and emphasises competition, innovation, and profitability. The company envisions the energy transition by focusing on significant investments in renewables, grid modernization, and electrification. For this narrative, innovation is key to overcoming technical challenges and finding cost-effective solutions for the energy transition. **The just transition (civil society people-powered) storyline**, informed by national surveys and advocacy reports, we anticipate that it prioritises equity, social justice, and community participation. This narrative might emphasise also a just transition for workers and communities, rapid renewable deployment with community ownership, ambitious climate action, energy efficiency, environmental protection, corporate accountability, public ownership, local action, and global solidarity.

Figure 1: Iterative process of integrating storylines to energy modelling tools (adapted from Trutnevyte et al., 2014)

From the three storylines, six themes were detected to guide the processes of translation to quantitative input assumptions that can be integrated into the energy and environmental modelling tools of Calliope-ENBIOS. For each of these themes, quantitative indicators have been assigned based on collected data and analysed data sets. Figure 1 provides a visualisation of the iterative process of integrating the storylines into the modelling of this study.

The **six themes** with their respective quantifiable indicators are the following:

- (1) Renewable energy deployment
 - a. % share of centralized vs. decentralized capacity

- b. Number of subsidies and incentives for renewable energy deployment
- (2) Citizen Energy
 - a. % of prosumerism and their electricity production
 - b. Ownership of renewable energy capacity
- (3) Barriers to infrastructure development
 - a. Duration of project developments
 - b. % of the duration of grid developments
 - c. Duration of proceeding and project litigation
 - d. Number of permits required for renewable energy projects
- (4) Social equality and job creation
 - a. Number of training slots for transitioning workers in specific sectors
 - b. The average reduction in energy bills for low-income households
 - c. Poverty rates
 - d. Income inequalities
- (5) Public participation and acceptance
 - a. Number of public hearings and stakeholder consultations held
 - b. Public opinion survey score on perceived benefits and impacts of the energy transition
- (6) Environmental impacts perceptions
 - a. Perceived severity of environmental problems
 - b. Perceived benefits of renewable energy
 - c. Concerns about potential environmental impacts (landscape, energy storage, land use, biodiversity)
 - d. Support for policy approaches (public ownership, carbon pricing, etc.)

DISCUSSION

Traditional energy models primarily focus on technical and economic aspects of the transition, neglecting its significant social and political implications. Recognising and incorporating them is crucial because they can profoundly influence the rate, scale, and feasibility of the energy transition. This study integrated qualitative storylines representing contrasting governance logics - Technocratic, Market-Driven, and Just Transition - with quantitative indicators within the Caliope-ENBIOS modelling tools. By doing so, we explore the potential social, political, and economic implications of the Spanish energy transition beyond the conventional techno-economic lens.

This research holds significant social relevance as it incorporates diverse stakeholders' perspectives. Hence, it ensures that the energy scenarios run by the modelling tool of ENBIOS are reflective of various interests within Spanish society and aligned with societal values and needs.

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, this study explored the potential of integrating environmental perceptions, and social and political aspects into modelling by employing storylines of diverse governance logics within the Spanish energy transition. This study contributes to the valuation of environmental impacts in environmental impact modelling and the advancement of energy modelling by demonstrating the feasibility and importance of integrating social and political aspects. Moving beyond purely technical cost-efficient analysis, this approach allows for a more comprehensive and holistic understanding of the energy transition in Spain by incorporating indicators to reflect societal values and needs. As such, it can inform more equitable and sustainable policy decisions while also fostering greater stakeholder engagement and social inclusion throughout the energy transition process. Hence, it is a step further towards understanding the multi-layered nature of the energy transition, highlighting the essential balance between rapid decarbonisation, social equity, and public acceptance.

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